

ELECTROLYSIS OF MAGNESIUM SULPHATE IN THE PRÉSENCE OF SULPHURIC ACID

BY DUSHYANT NARASINGASA SOLANKI AND PIDAPARTHI SURYANARAYANA SASTRY

A study has been made of the electrolysis of aqueous $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the presence of varying proportions of H_2SO_4 . The influence on the production of persulphate of the following factors has been investigated: composition of the electrolyte, inter-electrode distance, current density at the anode and the cathode, temperature, duration of electrolysis, addition agents and cathode material. Data are also given for the optimum conditions for the production of the persalt. High yields of persulphate under studied conditions are attributed to the absence of Caro's acid.

The probable mechanism of the formation of magnesium persulphate is also indicated.

Persulphates and hydrogen peroxide on account of their industrial importance form a subject of great interest. The electrolysis of sulphuric acid gives perdisulphuric acid, $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (Marshall's acid), which hydrolyses into permonosulphuric acid, H_2SO_5 (Caro's acid), and subsequently into hydrogen peroxide and sulphuric acid. This process, though simple, is not advantageous due to the rapid falling off of the current efficiency (C. E.) with the prolongation of electrolysis as Marshall's acid, and more especially Caro's acid, are comparatively unstable than the persulphates. Müller and Schellhaas (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1907, 13, 257; 1908, 14, 121) have shown that in the case of electrolysis of sulphuric acid, the C. E. decreases rapidly and falls even to zero, the rate of formation of Marshall's acid being equal to the rate of decomposition of Caro's acid. The state at which the total amount of peracids remains constant is known as "steady state". It was thought that this difficulty of comparative instability of Marshall's acid, and particularly of Caro's acid, might be overcome by employing MgSO_4 in H_2SO_4 medium as the starting material. From magnesium persulphate hydrogen peroxide can be prepared by its decomposition with H_2SO_4 and hydrolysis under suitable conditions and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure.

L. Li and K. Pei (*Contr. Chem. Nat. Acad., Peiping*, 1935, 2, 1-20) have shown that in the case of the electrolytic preparation of magnesium persulphate an anodic current density of 70 amp./dm². gives the optimum yield. Work has been in progress in the Electrochemical Laboratories of the Benares Hindu University for some considerable time on the electro-preparation of hydrogen peroxide from H_2SO_4 (Solanki and Sheshadri, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1942, Part III, p. 43) and from Na_2SO_4 in the presence of sulphuric acid (Joshi, Solanki and Kamath, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 24A, 305). The present investigation is in continuation of this line of research and an attempt has been made to find the suitability of MgSO_4 as the starting material. The influence of the various factors, such as the bath composition, temperature of electrolysis on the C. E. of the persulphate formation has been fully investigated and the optimum conditions established.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrolytic cell consisted of a cylindrical glass jar 10" x 4", closed with a rubber stopper, through which two glass tubes supporting platinum electrodes, a thermometer

and an exit tube for the escape of gases were passed. Current was tapped from the mains and was regulated by a rheostat and lamp resistance. The current was recorded by a precision ammeter arranged in series and P. D. of the cell by a voltmeter connected across the two electrodes. The temperature of the electrolytic cell was kept constant at the desired value (usually 10°); 50 c.c. of the solution were taken for electrolysis each time. Usually a current of one ampere was passed for half an hour. After the electrolysis the cell was gently shaken to make the solution uniform and 5 c.c. of the electrolyte were estimated for total active oxygen by the familiar $\text{FeSO}_4\text{-KMnO}_4$ method in an atmosphere of CO_2 with the usual precautions (Readwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II. 7th ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1930, p. 535).

The influence on the C. E. for the persulphate formation of the following factors was studied :

- (1) Conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in neutral solutions.
- (2) Conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in H_2SO_4 solution (25 g./100 c.c.).
- (3) Conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in H_2SO_4 solution (60 g./100 c.c.).
- (4) Conc. of H_2SO_4 along with $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ soln. (45 g./100 c.c.).
- (5) Anodic current density.
- (6) Cathodic current density.
- (7) Inter-electrode distance.
- (8) Use of diaphragm.
- (9) Duration of electrolysis.
- (10) Temperature of electrolysis.
- (11) Addition agents.
- (12) Cathode material.

The results obtained are shown in Tables I to XII and graphically in curves I to IV in Figure 1.

TABLE I

Influence of concentration of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on current efficiency.

Anodic current density = 60.6 amp/dm². Current passed = 1 amp. Cathodic current density = 29.3 amp./dm². Duration of electrolysis = 30 mins. Vol. of electrolyte = 50.0 c.c. Inter-electrode distance = 3.1 cm. Temp. = 10° .

$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 c.c. soln.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20\text{-KMnO}_4$)	Diaphragm not used.	
			C. R.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
10 g.	4.0 volts	0	0%	0 g.
30	4.1	0	0	0
50	4.2	0	0	0
70	4.3	8	2.2	2

TABLE II

Influence of conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in H_2SO_4 soln. (25 g./100 c.c. soln.) on current efficiency.

Conditions, same as in Table I.

$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 c.c. soln.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20\text{-KMnO}_4$)	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
20 g.	4.6 volts.	41	11.0%	7.13 g.
30	4.6	46	12.2	8.00
40	4.7	68	18.2	11.57
45	4.8	71	19.1	11.83
50	4.8	71	19.1	11.83

TABLE III

Influence of conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in H_2SO_4 medium (60 g./100 c.c. soln.) on current efficiency.

Conditions, same as in Table I.

$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 c.c. soln.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20\text{-KMnO}_4$)	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
20 g.	4.6 volts	20.5	55.0 %	35.65 g.
30	5.3	23.4	62.7	35.32
40	5.8	24.2	64.8	33.38
45	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
50	6.4	25.4	68.1	31.75

TABLE IV

Influence of conc. of H_2SO_4 on current efficiency.

Conc. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} = 45$ g./100 c.c. of soln. Other conditions, as in Table I.

H_2SO_4 in 100 c.c. of soln.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20\text{-KMnO}_4$)	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
20 g.	5.2 volts	5.4	14.5 %	8.31 g.
25	5.4	12.9	19.1	18.11
40	5.6	16.6	44.5	23.71
60	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
65	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
70	7.0	24.5	65.7	28.00

TABLE V

Influence of anodic current density on C. E.

Composition of electrolyte used = 45 g. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 60 g. of H_2SO_4 (in 100 c.c. of soln). Current varied as indicated in the first column.

Other conditions, same as in Table I (except anodic C. D.).

Current passed.	Anodic C. D. (amps./dm ²).	P. D.	Active O ₂ in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of N/20-KMnO ₄).	C. E.	Active O ₂ per K. W. H.
0.3 amp.	18.2	4.0 volts	6.0	53.6 %	40.00 g.
0.5	39.3	4.6	11.3	60.6	39.30
1.0	60.6	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
2.0	121.2	9.0	44.8	60.0	19.80
3.0	181.8	10.0	63.7	56.9	16.98

TABLE VI

Influence of cathodic current density on C. E.

Anodic C. D. = 60.6 amp./dm². Current used = 1 amp.
Other conditions, same as in Table V.

Cathodic C. D. (amp./dm ²).	P. D.	Active O ₂ in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of N/20-KMnO ₄).	C. E.	Active O ₂ per K. W. H.
16.0	5.8 volts	25.0	67.0 %	34.48 g.
29.3	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
83.0	7.3	24.4	65.5	26.74

TABLE VII

Influence of inter-electrode distance on C. E.

Cathodic C. D. = 29.3 amps./dm². Other conditions same as in Table V.

Inter-electrode distance.	P. D.	Active O ₂ in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of N/20-KMnO ₄).	C. E.	Active O ₂ per K. W. H.
1.1 cm.	5.3 volts	24.3	65.2 %	36.68 g.
3.1	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
4.0	7.3	26.7	71.3	29.26

TABLE VIII

Influence of diaphragm on C. E.

Anode placed in 50 c.c. of soln. placed in earthenware diaphragm, cathode in 60% H_2SO_4 soln. placed in outer glass cylinder. Inter-electrode distance=3.1 cm. Other conditions, same as in Table VII.

Expt No.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20-KMnO_4$).	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
1	9.1 volts	30.6	82.1 %	26.90 g.
2*	9.4	33.5	90.0	28.42

*In this experiment KF (1 g./100 c.c. soln.) is used as addition agent along with the diaphragm.

TABLE IX

Influence of duration of electrolysis on C. E.

Inter-electrode distance=3.1 cm. Other conditions, same as in Table VII.

Duration.	P. D.	Active O_2 in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20-KMnO_4$).	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
15 min.	6.3 ² volts	13.0	69.8 %	36.19 g.
30	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
60	6.3	45.7	61.3	29.02
90	6.3	63.8	57.0	25.77
120	6.3	80.7	54.1	25.62
240	6.3	130.0	43.5	20.63

TABLE X

Influence of temperature on C. E.

Duration of electrolysis=30 minutes. Other conditions, same as in Table IX.

Temp.	P. D.	Active O_2 in c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of $N/20-KMnO_4$).	C. E.	Active O_2 per K. W. H.
5°	6.8 volts	25.4	68.1 %	29.88 g.
10°	6.3	25.0	67.0	31.76
15°	5.9	25.0	67.0	33.90
20°	5.6	22.5	60.3	32.14
30°	5.0	17.5	46.9	28.00
40°	4.8	12.3	33.0	20.50
50°	4.5	6.5	17.5	11.96
60°	4.3	2.8	7.5	5.21

TABLE XI

Influence of addition reagents on C. E.

Temperature of electrolysis = 10°. Addition agent in 100 c.c. of soln. = 1 g. Other conditions, same as in Table X.

Addition agent added.	P. D.	Active O ₂ in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of N/20-KMnO ₄).	C. E.	Active O ₂ per K. W. H.
Nil	6.3 volts	25.0	67.0 %	31.76 g.
KF	6.4	27.8	74.6	34.75
Na ₂ HPO ₄	6.2	26.8	71.9	34.59
HCl (conc.)	6.0	26.6	71.4	35.47
TiO ₂	6.3	25.3	70.5	33.40
V ₂ O ₅	6.3	26.1	70.0	33.14
CeO ₂	6.3	25.7	68.9	32.63
Na ₂ SO ₄	6.1	24.7	66.3	32.40
WO ₃	6.3	24.4	65.5	30.98
CaCl ₂	6.3	23.6	63.3	29.84
Pb(CH ₃ COO) ₂	6.1	23.5	63.0	30.82
ThO ₂	6.3	22.7	60.8	28.82
Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	6.2	22.6	60.6	29.16
CoSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	6.8	22.2	59.5	26.12
NaBr	5.9	21.4	57.4 ^b	29.02
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	5.7	18.6	49.8	26.11
MnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	6.2	17.9	48.1	23.23
Tl(CH ₃ COO)	6.1	16.4	44.0	21.51
AgNO ₃	6.0	0	0	0

TABLE XII

Influence of cathode material on C. E.

Duration of electrolysis = 30 mins. Platinum electrode used in all the above series of experiments substituted by cheap materials. Other conditions, same as in Table X.

Cathode material.	P. D.	Active O ₂ in 5 c.c. of electrolyte soln. (in c.c. of N/20-KMnO ₄).	C. E.	Active O ₂ per K. W. H.
Platinum	6.3 volts.	25.0	67.0 %	31.76 g.
Brass	6.0	24.1	64.6	32.33
Lead	8.5	25.3	67.8	23.81
Graphite	7.0	24.8	66.5	28.34
Cadmium	7.0	25.1	67.3	28.68

DISCUSSION

Our foregoing results shown in Tables I to XII clearly indicate that the production of persulphates electrochemically is dependent on a wide variety of factors such as the composition of the electrolyte, the current density and the temperature, etc. When a neutral solution of magnesium sulphate was electrolysed between platinum electrodes at the operating conditions of temperature (10°) and current density (60.6 amp./dm².) there was copious evolution of oxygen and hydrogen at the respective electrodes, accompanied by a faint smell of ozone, but practically there was no formation of persulphate (C. E. 2.2%). The presence of sulphuric acid, however, exerted marked influence on the formation of persulphuric acid (*cf.* Tables II and III).

Various views regarding the formation of persulphuric acid and persulphates exist in the literature. Of these the more important ones may be discussed. The dissociation of sulphuric acid in water takes place in two stages :

Reaction (1) is favoured by high concentration of the acid, whereas, reaction (2) is favoured in dilute solutions. By the polymerisation of HSO_4^- ions (Richarz, *Wied. Ann.*, 1885, 24, 183; *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 166), perdisulphuric acid, ($\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, Marshall's acid) is formed according to the equation,

It follows therefore that a high concentration of HSO_4^- (ions) is the chief prerequisite if high yields of persulphate are required.

The unusually high yields of the persalt in the case of slightly acidic solutions of ammonium sulphate, where there is little probability of the presence of HSO_4^- ions, were tacitly assumed by Essin (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1933, 39, 891) to be due to the polymerisation of SO_4^{2-} ions according to the reaction,

An alternative general mechanism was suggested by Foerster ("Electrochemie Wasseriger Losungen", 1922, p. 842)

and in the particular case of the electrolysis of ammonium sulphate,

Very low (2.2%) or practically no production of persulphate obtained by the electrolysis of neutral solutions of magnesium sulphate might be attributed to the absence of HSO_4^- ions which are necessary [*cf.* reaction (3)]. With the progressive addition of sulphuric acid, however, the yield of persulphate increased steadily (*cf.* curve I, Fig 1). For example, the increase of concentration of H_2SO_4 from 20% to 60% with a concomitant increase of HSO_4^- ions increases the C. E. from 14.5% to 67%. Thus, it appears that

the formation of magnesium persulphate might, perhaps, be due to the following reactions. Magnesium sulphate in the presence of H_2SO_4 might form an acid sulphate,

thus accounting for the formation of magnesium persulphate. Even in slightly acidified solutions, progressive addition of $MgSO_4$ produces a corresponding increase in the C. E. (cf. Tables II, III and IV).

Variation of C. D. at the anode plays a very important rôle in all electrochemical oxidation reactions, especially in the formation of persulphates and persulphuric acid. A high anodic C. D. favours a high yield of persulphate. This is revealed by our results shown in Table V (curve No. II). This might probably be due to the discharge potential of HSO_4^- ions being higher than that of SO_4^{--} ions or of oxygen. Our results indicate that optimum yields of persulphate are obtained at C. D. of 68 amp./dm². It may also be probable that the close packing of HSO_4^- ions, which might result at such high anodic C. D., might contribute to an increase in the C. E. The variation of C. D. at the cathode (cf. Table VI) shows very little influence on the C. E. of persulphate formation.

FIG. I

In oxidation reactions in a cell without a diaphragm, the oxidation products formed at the anode might diffuse to the cathode and get reduced by the nascent hydrogen

released at the cathode. An increase in the inter-electrode distance, it is to be anticipated, might minimise the possible reduction at the cathode and thereby increase the yield of persulphate, a deduction in close accord with our experimental results (cf. Table VIII). This is further supported by our results showing marked increase in the C. E. from 67% to 82.1% by carrying out the electrolysis in a diaphragm cell which prevented the oxidised products from being reduced by diffusion. But it should also be noted that with the use of diaphragm, the P. D. across the cell increases considerably from 6.3 to 9.1 volts. This brings about an increase in the consumption of electrical energy which is not technically desirable.

Our results in Table IX (cf. Fig 1, curve III) indicate that the C. E. falls gradually with progressive duration of electrolysis, but this fall is very much less steep than what is obtained in the case of electrolysis of H_2SO_4 (Solanki and Sheshadri, unpublished work). In the electrolysis of 60% H_2SO_4 a 'steady state' is reached after a comparatively short time, practically there being no further increase in the amount of persulphuric acid with the prolongation of electrolysis, the rate of formation of persulphuric acid being equal to the rate of destruction of the peracid, especially Caro's acid (*vide supra*). This is due to the conversion of $H_2S_2O_8$ into highly unstable (readily decomposing) Caro's acid, which might also function as a depolariser, thus reducing the C. E.

But in the electrolysis of a solution containing 45% $MgSO_4 \cdot 7 H_2O$ and 60% H_2SO_4 , our results indicate that the C. E. remains sufficiently high even after longer intervals and there is no attainment of the steady state. This might perhaps be due to the absence of Caro's acid and also due to the fact that the cation Mg^{++} might inhibit the decomposition of the persulphate ion, $S_2O_8^{--}$, and thereby stabilise the product.

The variation of temperature affects the yield of persulphate considerably. In general, low temperatures are favourable for high yields of persulphates (cf. Table X, Fig 1, curve IV). The C. E. is fairly constant between 5° and 15°. At higher temperatures the persalt MgS_2O_8 might undergo the decomposition due to the reaction with H_2SO_4 forming $H_2S_2O_8$, the latter undergoing stepwise hydrolytic decomposition and chemical decomposition [cf. equations (10), (11), (12)] and this might lower the yields of the persalts.

Addition agents like KF, HF, HCl show pronounced beneficial effect in improving the yield of the persulphate obtained electrolytically.

The function of these substances is probably due to

(1) an increase of anode potential, and (2) destruction of Caro's acid chemically thus preventing its depolarisation or chemical decomposition.

The amount of addition agent added in each of these experiments was 1 g. per 100 c.c. of the solution and the order of their influence was as : $KF > Na_2HPO_4 > HCl > TiO_2 > V_2O_5 > CeO_2$ etc. The highly beneficial effect of KF might be due to

the slight increase in the anodic potential. HCl and Na_2HPO_4 increased the C. E., though the P. D. decreased, probably due to chemical destruction of Caro's acid. $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ reduced the C. E. considerably, processes other than the formation of $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, such as cyclic oxidation and reduction of Mn and Co ions might be taking place. With the addition of AgNO_3 , however, the yield dropped down to zero. This marked inhibitory action of AgNO_3 might, perhaps, be due to a lowering of the anodic potential from 6.3 to 6.0 volts or to its catalytic action on the decomposition of the persalts, no sooner they are formed. By the addition of KF to the electrolyte in a diaphragm cell, the C. E. might be raised to as high a value as 92% (cf. Table VIII).

An attempt was made to find out cheap substitutes in place of platinum as the cathode material. Several cathodes were tried and results showed (cf. Table XII) that the operation was smooth with platinum cathode and the P. D. (corresponding energy consumption) was minimum for the same yield of the persalt.

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ELECTROCHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY.

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